

WETTING ALONG FIBER(S) PLACED ON SOLID SUBSTRATE

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ABSTRACT

A special attention is paid to the wetting process along glass fiber(s) settled on the solid substrate. We prepare several kinds of test fluids of different viscosity and surface tensions. The tip velocity and the profile of the liquid propagating between the fiber(s) and the substrate are evaluated through the observations. We make a comparison of the profile and the macroscopic-contact-line velocity of the droplet spreading on the substrate as functions of the test-fluid properties and the distance between the fiber and the substrate.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wetting of the fibers by capillary force is very important in the manufacturing process of the fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP). In the system of vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), the resin is driven by the pressure difference within fiber bundles. Generally the bundles are settled on the substrate, and then are tightly covered with the bagging film by sucking the air inside the film. It was found that the stitching yarns bundling the fibers realize a complex flow field of the resin, which results in the flow of the resin against the pressure difference inside the fiber bundles [1]. In addition, at the bottom of the fiber bundles, the fibers and/or stitching yarn have positions very close to the substrate. This also brings a significant effect on the wetting process of the resin along the fiber. Such complex flow structures along the fiber bundles in the molding process would cause voids where the resin has not penetrated between the fibers. There exist a number of studies on the wetting on the substrate [2], on the deformation of the meniscus moving along a vertical plate [3], on the wetting along a fiber [4], on the capillary rise in the yarn and so on. Small amount of information, on the other hand, has been accumulated on the wetting between the fiber(s) and the substrate. In the present study, a special attention is paid to the wetting process along fiber(s) settled on the solid substrate.

2 EXPERIMENTS

We prepare three kinds of glass fibers of different diameter d ; 24, 17 and 13 μm . Silicon wafer covered by SiO_2 is employed as the test substrate, which enables us to prepare a flat and smooth substrate. We employ four different kinds of liquid as the test fluids; that is, epoxy resin of 342 cSt, and silicone oil of 100, 500 and 1000 cSt in kinetic viscosity. A fiber is settled above the substrate at the designated height h in a range of 5 to 360 μm , and a droplet of 2 μl is calmly placed. The propagation process of the liquid is observed with two CCD cameras simultaneously at 30 frame-per-second (fps); the one for the side view, and the other for the top view (see Fig. 1). The tip velocity and the profile of the liquid propagating between the fiber and the substrate are evaluated through the observations.

3 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Typical example of the observation of the droplet spreading along a fiber on the substrate is shown in Fig. 2. This indicates the case of $h = 230 \mu\text{m}$, $d = 24 \mu\text{m}$ and the resin as the test fluid. One can clearly see that we have two macroscopic contact lines (M-CLs in the figure) in the case of large h , that is, the macroscopic contact line advancing along the fiber, and the macroscopic contact line

advancing on the substrate.

We thus can define the velocity of the macroscopic contact lines as a function of the height of the fiber on the substrate, the fiber diameter, the ambient temperature and the test fluid. Figure 3 illustrates the temporal variations of the velocity of the macroscopic contact line of the droplet spreading along a fiber placed at $h \sim 0 \mu\text{m}$. The figure consists of the data under different temperature of the system. The velocity decreases drastically as a function of time and gradually converge to the null velocity. We make a comparison of the velocity of the macroscopic contact line of the droplet spreading on the substrate without the fiber. It is found that the velocity of the macroscopic contact line of the droplet on the substrate in the case of small height of the fiber becomes much larger. In the case of the large height of the fiber from the substrate, on the other hand, the velocity is drastically decreased to prevent the wetting on the substrate.

Figure 1: Schematic of experimental apparatus

Figure 2: Typical example of the observation of the droplet spreading along a fiber on the substrate: $h = 230 \mu\text{m}$, $d = 24 \mu\text{m}$ and the resin as the test fluid.

Figure 3: Effects of the system temperature and the fiber diameter on the temporal variation of the velocity of the macroscopic contact line of the droplet spreading along a fiber on the substrate under $h \sim 0 \mu\text{m}$. Solid marks correspond to the results in the case of $d = 24 \mu\text{m}$, and the nulls correspond to the results in the case of $d = 13 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 4: (a) Droplet profile near the macroscopic contact lines on the substrate and on the fiber placed at $h = 264 \mu\text{m}$, and (b) the droplet profiles near the contact lines as a function of the height of the fiber above the substrate. All data correspond to the results under the diameter of the fiber $d = 24 \mu\text{m}$ and the system temperature $T_{\text{sys}} = 22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

We also focus on the profile of the droplet spreading along a fiber. Figure 4 indicates the typical examples of the profiles of the droplet near the macroscopic contact lines on the substrate and the on the fiber placed at h above the substrate. It is noted that the direction of the resin flow on the substrate is opposite to that shown in Fig. 2 in order to define the position of the macroscopic contact line of the droplet on the substrate as 0. Frame (a) illustrates a typical result under $h = 264 \mu\text{m}$. The macroscopic contact line on the substrate advances faster than that on the fiber, so that the droplet forms a ‘tongue’

ahead the macroscopic contact line on the fiber. The shapes of the tongue, or the profiles of the droplet between the macroscopic contact lines under various h are illustrated in frame (b). The profiles are indicated starting from the position of the macroscopic contact line on the substrate. It is found that the distance between the macroscopic contact lines (ΔD in the figure) becomes larger as the height of the fiber. This reflects that the difference of the wettability of the substrate and the fiber. The larger curvature in the case of lower position of the fiber realizes a significant drive of the resin because of the Laplace pressure.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

We focus on the wetting behaviors of glass fiber-resin system. Wetting of fiber by capillary force is very important in the manufacturing process of the fiber reinforced plastics (FRP). In this study, we settle a droplet on fiber(s) on a silicon substrate, and investigate the wetting of fiber by capillary force. The tip velocity and the profile of the liquid propagating between the fiber(s) and the substrate are evaluated through the observations. We make a comparison of the profile and the macroscopic-contact-line velocity of the droplet spreading on the substrate as functions of the test-fluid properties and the distance between the fiber and the substrate. It is found that the velocity of the macroscopic contact line of the droplet on the substrate in the case of small height of the fiber becomes much larger. In the case of the large height of the fiber from the substrate, on the other hand, the velocity is drastically decreased to prevent the wetting on the substrate. We also indicate the effect of the distance between the fiber and the substrate on the profile of the droplet spreading on the substrate.

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